

INSTRUCTIONAL GUIDE MANUAL FOR BRINE SHRIMP COUNTING APPARATUS

Brine shrimp (*Artemia*) serve as an alternative animal model for assessing the toxicity of various compounds, particularly plant extracts. However, manually counting large numbers of *Artemia* can be tedious and time-consuming. This brine shrimp counting apparatus is designed to facilitate quick and accurate counting, improving efficiency in toxicity studies.

Brine Shrimp
counting apparatus
for lethality test

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User Manual for Brine Shrimp Counting Apparatus

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1. Overview

Brine shrimp (*Artemia*) serve as an alternative animal model for assessing the toxicity of various compounds, particularly plant extracts. However, manually counting large numbers of *Artemia* can be tedious and time-consuming. This brine shrimp counting apparatus is designed to facilitate quick and accurate counting, improving efficiency in toxicity studies.

2. List of Parts and Their Functions

- Base and Adjustable Shaft – Provides stability and allows height adjustments for optimal positioning of tanks.
- Adjustable Lamp – Enhances visibility during the counting process.
- Lens – Aids in magnification for accurate counting.
- Seawater Tank – Holds clean seawater for dilution and cleaning.
- Brine Shrimp Tank – Contains the *Artemia* suspension for counting.
- Plastic Probe – Regulates the controlled release of brine shrimp for counting.

3. Setup Instructions

1. Mounting the Tanks:

- The apparatus features a hanger at the top of the adjustable shaft, allowing the seawater tank (Figure 3.1) and brine shrimp tanks (Figure 3.2) to be securely hanged.
- The shaft's height can be adjusted to control the positioning of the tanks.

2. Assembling the Components:

- Plug the adjustable lamp into a DC 240V power source.
- Fix the lens into the designated lens holder for clear magnification.
- Attach the two separate tanks to the Y-shaped glass tube for controlled fluid distribution. (Figure 3.3)

3. Connecting the Emission System:

- The plastic emission probe, located at the end of the wire line, releases brine shrimp in a controlled manner.
- A cannula holder at the end of the probe allows for the attachment of a suitable cannula.
- The flow controller, located at the top of the emission probe, regulates the release rate of brine shrimp. (Figure 3.4)

Figure 3.1

Figure 3.2

Figure 3.3

Figure 3.4

4. Operating Procedure

1. Filling the Tanks:

- Pour brine shrimp suspension into the small brine shrimp tank.
- Fill the larger seawater tank with clean seawater.

2. Counting Process:

- Adjust the probe flow controller to release brine shrimp dropwise.
- Observe and count the shrimp as they pass through the system.

3. Dilution and Cleaning:

- If dilution of the brine shrimp suspension is required, adjust the seawater controller to regulate the flow of clean seawater.
- Use the seawater controller to flush the system after counting.

5. Maintenance and Troubleshooting

1. Handling the Apparatus:

- Always lift the apparatus by its base, not by the shaft, to prevent damage.

2. Cleaning the System:

- After each use, flush the system with seawater using the tank controllers to remove any residual shrimp or debris.

3. Storage:

- After use, disassemble all parts and store them separately in a dry, clean space.

6. Safety Precautions

- The probe is attached to a cannula, posing a risk of needle-prick injuries. Handle with care.
- When capping the cannula after use, ensure proper technique to avoid accidental injury.